

Synthesis of some New Derivatives of Imidazole Compounds

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The reaction of 1-substituted-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-5-imidazolones with different nucleophilic reagents has been studied. The new compounds synthesised showed certain biological activities.

THE chemistry of imidazole compounds is receiving much attention in recent years. This is principally due to the unique physical and chemical properties of such compounds, which gained them wide application as plant growth regulators¹, dyes² and corrosion inhibitors³. More significant to us is their medicinal application as agents for controlling various mycoses⁴.

It is mentioned that a condensed isoxazole or pyrazole ring to the imidazole nucleus is expected to wide the scope of its biological application as pharmaceutical and parasitological agents^{5,6}. Consequently, in the present investigation, several pyrazolo and isoxazolo imidazoles were prepared and preliminarily tested against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria as well as against certain fungi.

2-Phenyl-4-arylidene-5-oxazolone⁷ (1a-c) upon treatment with ammonia or aliphatic amines afforded the corresponding imidazoline⁸ (2a-h).

The activation exerted by the carbonyl group on the exocyclic double bond in these compounds render them susceptible for the addition of various amino compounds, e.g. phenylhydrazine, hydrazine hydrate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

N-Acetylpyrazolino [3,4-*d*]imidazoline derivatives (3a-h) were obtained from the reaction of 2a-h with hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid. The structure of 3a-h were established based on its analytical and spectral data⁹. Phenylhydrazine reacted with 2a-h in ethanol in the presence of piperidine as basic catalyst giving *N*-phenylpyrazolino[3,4-*d*]imidazoline derivatives (4a-h). Compounds 4 proved stable on boiling with acetic acid, mixing with concentrated sulphuric acid at room temperature or heating above their melting points, which are the conditions that bring out the cyclisation of phenylhydrazones to pyrazolines. In addition, as ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution of 2a-h reacted with hydroxylamine

Scheme 1

hydrochloride to afford the isoxazolino[3,4-d]imidazole derivatives (5a-h) (Scheme 1).

2a, e, h, were further condensed with substituted cinnamoyl chloride in dry benzene in the presence of triethylamine as a catalyst to give the corresponding 1-cinnamoyl-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-2-imidazolin-5-one derivatives (6a-f). 6a-f were also obtained via the reaction of 1-acetyl-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-2-imidazolin-5-one derivatives 7a, e, h, with substituted benzaldehyde. 6a-f, in turn, upon treatment with hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine afforded the corresponding derivatives 8a-f, 9a-f and 10a-f, respectively (Scheme 2).

Physical and analytical data of the compounds are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Biological testing: Samples of the selected members of compounds 3, 4, 5, 8, 9 and 10 were dissolved in ethylene glycol and transferred to filter paper discs. The antibacterial activity was then determined against gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli*

and the gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus cereus* (B.c), *Bacillus sterothermophilus* (B.t) and *Sarcina lutea* (S.l). The antifungal activity of the same selected compounds were determined against *Aspergillus egypticus* (A.e) and *Penicillium cyclopium* (P.c). The results are listed in Table 3, and it can be seen that the applied imidazole compounds including *N*-acetylpyrazoline, *N*-phenylpyrazoline and isoxazoline nuclei possess reasonable biological activities against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, and their effect being higher against the positive ones. The *N*-phenylpyrazolines (4a, h, g, and 10) have generally higher sensitivity than *N*-acetylpyrazolines (3d, f, and 8). Replacement of the NH groups of 3c and 4a by methyl and by ethyl of compounds 3f, 4h and 5g, increase the activity of these compound towards gram-positive bacteria and fungi. Substitution of the substituted-aryl moiety have a great effect on the bacteriostatic and fungicidal activities. Furthermore compounds 8, 9 and 10 show high biological activity which was anticipated from its structure.

a) X=H; Y=H
 b) X=H; Y=p-NO₂
 c) X=p-NO₂; Y=H
 d) X=p-NO₂; Y=p-NO₂
 e) X=p-OH; Y=H
 f) X=p-OH; Y=p-NO₂

Scheme 2

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3-5

Compd. no.	R	X	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
3a	H	H	220	60	71.02 (71.00)	5.25 (5.26)	18.44 (18.42)
b	H	p-OH	230	80	67.51 (67.5)	5.08 (5.00)	17.51 (17.5)
c	H	p-NO ₂	240	65	61.88 (61.89)	4.28 (4.29)	20.04 (20.05)
d	OH ₂	H	260	50	71.62 (71.60)	5.66 (5.66)	17.63 (17.60)
e	OH ₂	p-NO ₂	320	63	62.81 (62.80)	4.68 (4.68)	19.29 (19.28)
f	C ₂ H ₅	H	180	65	72.21 (72.20)	6.08 (6.02)	16.81 (16.80)
g	C ₂ H ₅	p-OH	279	71	68.97 (68.96)	5.76 (5.74)	16.08 (16.09)
h	C ₂ H ₅	p-NO ₂	285	80	63.67 (63.66)	5.04 (5.03)	18.61 (18.50)
4a	H	H	180	72	78.08 (78.10)	5.91 (5.92)	16.57 (16.56)
b	H	p-OH	220	70	74.37 (74.36)	5.36 (5.35)	15.78 (15.77)
c	H	p-NO ₂	175	56	68.73 (68.75)	4.69 (4.68)	18.21 (18.22)
d	OH ₂	H	195	50	78.3 (78.4)	5.69 (5.68)	15.9 (15.9)
e	OH ₂	p-NO ₂	150	63	69.53 (69.52)	4.71 (4.70)	17.62 (17.60)
f	C ₂ H ₅	H	150	65	79.37 (79.36)	5.32 (5.32)	14.80 (14.81)
g	C ₂ H ₅	p-OH	220	75	76.20 (76.10)	5.57 (5.58)	14.23 (14.20)
h	C ₂ H ₅	p-NO ₂	280	70	70.91 (70.90)	5.21 (5.20)	16.61 (16.50)
5a	H	H	170	50	73.0 (73.0)	4.95 (4.94)	15.95 (15.96)
b	H	p-OH	230	40	68.82 (68.81)	4.64 (4.65)	15.08 (15.05)
c	H	p-NO ₂	270	45	62.28 (62.30)	3.88 (3.89)	18.19 (18.18)
d	OH ₂	H	320	40	73.7 (73.6)	5.42 (5.41)	15.15 (15.16)
e	OH ₂	p-NO ₂	240	55	63.29 (63.30)	4.33 (4.34)	17.38 (17.39)
f	C ₂ H ₅	H	215	50	74.21 (74.22)	5.83 (5.84)	14.39 (14.40)
g	C ₂ H ₅	p-OH	320	60	70.34 (70.35)	5.52 (5.53)	13.67 (13.68)
h	C ₂ H ₅	p-NO ₂	300	69	64.18 (64.20)	4.77 (4.76)	16.66 (16.66)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 8-10

Compd. no.	X	Y	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
8a	H	H	175	46	75.8 (75.9)	5.49 (5.48)	11.60 (11.81)
b	H	p-NO ₂	120	42	69.44 (69.30)	4.67 (4.80)	13.49 (13.40)
c	p-NO ₂	H	160	38	69.39 (69.36)	4.84 (4.81)	13.90 (13.80)
d	p-NO ₂	p-NO ₂	157	40	63.62 (63.30)	4.51 (4.25)	14.71 (14.80)
e	p-OH	H	135	24	73.57 (73.40)	5.51 (5.30)	11.46 (11.42)
f	p-OH	p-NO ₂	164	70	67.50 (67.38)	4.78 (4.67)	13.21 (13.08)

(Table 2 contd.)

9a	H	H	210	50	79.71 (79.50)	5.80 (5.87)	15.26 (15.05)
b	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	240	40	73.82 (73.60)	4.67 (4.80)	16.49 (16.25)
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	H	800	63	73.83 (73.60)	4.73 (4.80)	16.43 (16.25)
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	290	57	68.62 (68.50)	4.60 (4.30)	17.43 (17.28)
e	<i>p</i> -OH	H	90	52	77.63 (77.30)	5.29 (5.22)	14.90 (14.80)
f	<i>p</i> -OH	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	110	34	71.52 (71.70)	4.82 (4.68)	15.64 (15.80)
10a	H	H	150	80	73.82 (73.70)	4.83 (4.66)	13.62 (13.75)
b	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	125	30	66.42 (66.37)	3.78 (3.98)	15.60 (15.48)
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	H	196	74	66.70 (66.37)	3.72 (3.98)	15.61 (15.48)
d	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	135	70	60.43 (60.30)	3.70 (3.42)	16.72 (16.90)
e	<i>p</i> -OH	H	150	66	70.82 (70.90)	4.35 (4.49)	13.50 (13.23)
f	<i>p</i> -OH	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	145	80	64.34 (64.10)	3.90 (3.84)	14.81 (14.95)

TABLE 3—BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	<i>E.c</i>	<i>B.c</i>	<i>B.t</i>	<i>S.l</i>	<i>A.s</i>	<i>P.c</i>
2c	++	++	+++	+++	++	++
2h	+	+	++	++	+	-
3c	+	+	+	+	+	+
3d	-	+	-	+	-	-
3f	-	-	-	+	-	-
4a	-	-	-	-	-	-
4h	++	++	++++	++++	++	++
4g	+	+	+++	+++	+	+
5a	+	+	++	++	+	+
5g	++	++	+++	+++	++	+
3e	++	+	++	+++	+	+
8a	++	++	++++	+++	+++	+++
8c	++	++	+++	++	++	++
8e	+	+	+	+	+	+
9a	++	++	++++	++++	+	+
9c	++	+++	++++	++++	+	++
9e	++	++	++++	+++	+	++
10a	++	+	+++	++++	++	++
10c	++	+	+++	+++	++	++
10d	++	+	+++	+++	++	++

Experimental

Infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Unicam SP 2006 spectrophotometer. Melting point are uncorrected. Elemental analyses were done at Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University.

Hippuric acid, hippuric acid azlactone and 1-substituted-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-5-imidazolones were prepared by the reported procedures^{7,8}. Likewise, cinnamoyl chloride and substituted-cinnamoyl chloride were prepared by literature methods.

N-Acetylpyrazolines (3 and 8): A mixture of arylideneimidazolone (2 or 6; 0.1 mol) hydrazine hydrate (0.1 or 0.2 mol) and a few drops of glacial acetic acid in dioxan (25 ml) were heated under reflux for 3 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and *N*-acetylpyrazoline was filtered off and crystallised from benzene.

N-Phenylpyrazolines (4 and 9): 2 or 6 (1 mol) and phenylhydrazine (1 or 2 mol) were refluxed in dioxan (30 ml) containing a few drops of piperidine for 3 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and *N*-phenylpyrazoline was precipitated by petroleum ether. The product was filtered off, washed several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 80-100°) and crystallised from the proper solvent.

Isoxazolines (5 and 10): A mixture of 2 or 6 (0.1 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.1 or 0.2 mol), and a few pellets of sodium hydroxide in dioxan (30 ml) were heated under reflux for 3 h. The reaction mixture was filtered off, the precipitate washed thoroughly with dioxan, and isoxazoline precipitated from the filtrate by ether. The product was filtered off, washed several times with ether and recrystallised from the proper solvent.

1-Substituted-cinnamoyl-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-5-imidazolones (6):

(i) Substituted-cinnamoyl chloride (1 mol) in dioxan (20 ml) and triethylamine (1 mol) were refluxed with 2a, e, h (1 mol) for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered, the filtrate evaporated under vacuum and the residue crystallised from ether.

(ii) A mixture of equimolar amounts of 1-acetyl-2-phenyl-4-arylidene-5-imidazolones (7) and the appropriate aldehyde in ethanol (50 ml) and 2% NaOH solution (1 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then poured to cold water, the precipitate filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol.

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